

Chemical examination of *Pongamia pinnata* L. seeds

Meera, Bimla and S. B. Kalidhar*

Department of Chemistry and Physics, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar-125 004, India

E-mail : kalidhar@hau.nic.in

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The structure of a new compound isolated from the seeds of *Pongamia pinnata* L. has been elucidated to be 3',4'-dimethoxy(2'', 3'' : 7,8) furanoflavone (5). Four known compounds isolated have been identified as 2'-methoxy- β -hydroxyl (2'',3'' : 4',3') furanochalcone (1), karanjin (2), lanceolatin B (3) and pongaglabrone (4).

Pongamia, a genus of only one spp. (Indo-Malayan) : *Pongamia pinnata* L. (Syn. *Pongamia glabra* Vent.), belongs to the family Leguminosae and the sub-family Papilionaceae. It is generally grown as avenue tree. It is used medicinally in China, Indo-China, the Phillipine Islands, Australia and La Reunion¹. Seeds of the plant have very high medicinal value as these are useful in inflammations, pectoral diseases, chronic fevers and anaemia² and we have undertaken the reinvestigation of the seeds.

Results and discussion

The column chromatography of the methanolic extract of the seeds revealed the presence of five compounds (1-5). Out of these, 2'-methoxy- β -hydroxyl (2'',3'' : 4',3') furanochalcone³ (1), karanjin⁴ (2), lanceolatin B⁵ (3) and pongaglabrone⁶ (4) are known compounds.

Compound 5 was obtained as colourless crystalline solid. Colour reaction with Mg/HCl indicated the compound to be a flavone. Its UV spectrum (λ_{\max} 267 and 301 nm) supported the compound to be a furanoflavone⁷. The IR spectrum showed the presence of a carbonyl group (1629 cm^{-1}). The MS and elemental analysis suggested $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$ to be the molecular formula for the compound. Its ¹H NMR spectrum showed the presence of two doublets (*J* 2.0 Hz) at δ 7.75 and 7.16 for H-5'' and H-4' furano protons. A singlet at δ 6.77 was observed for H-3 proton and a multiplet was observed at δ 7.49 for H-6, H-2' and H-5' protons. A double doublet (*J* 7.5 and 2.5 Hz) at δ 7.90, was observed for H-6' proton. A doublet (*J* 7.5 Hz) at δ 7.93 was assignable to H-5. A singlet was observed for six protons at δ 4.09, which showed the presence of two methoxy groups. Based upon this data, compound 5 was assigned the structure 3',4'-dimethoxy (2'',3'' : 7,8) furano-flavone (5). The RDA fission in the MS fragmentation pattern suggested the

presence of methoxy groups in the B-ring by showing peaks at 160 (A-ring fragment) and 162 (B-ring fragment).

The antimicrobial activity of the various fractions incorporating hexane, benzene, ethyl acetate and methanolic fractions were determined against two fungi *Aspergillus niger* and *Fusarium solani* and one bacteria *Xanthomonas axonopodis* pv. *cyamopsidis* at 500, 1000, 1500 and 2000 ppm concentrations, and these fractions were found to be devoid of any pathogenic activity at the above mentioned concentrations.

Experimental

Seeds (5 kg) of *P. pinnata* were collected from Landscape, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar. The seeds were separated from the seed coat and then extracted first with hexane and then with methanol. The column chromatography of methanolic extract afforded five compounds (1-5). Elution with benzene-petroleum ether (1 : 3) afforded 2'-methoxy- β -hydroxyl (2'',3'' : 4',3') furanochalcone (1, 310 mg), ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 19) karanjin (2, 30 mg), lanceolatin B (3, 30 mg), pongaglabrone (4, 40 mg) and 3',4'-dimethoxy (2'',3'' : 7,8) furanoflavone (5, 20 mg). Melting points were determined on Ganson electrical melting point apparatus. IR spectra were recorded on Hitachi 570 infrared spectrophotometer using KBr. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker AC-300F 300 MHz NMR spectrophotometer using TMS as internal standard. Chemi-

cal shifts are given in δ (ppm) and CDCl_3 was used as solvent for taking NMR spectra. Mass spectra were recorded on VG-70S 11-250J GC-MS-DS mass spectrophotometer.

Compound **5** was obtained on elution with ethyl acetate-benzene (1 : 19). Yield 20 mg, m.p. 171–172° (Found : C, 70.79; H, 4.32. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$ required : C, 70.80; H, 4.34%); UV λ_{max} 267, 301 nm; IR ν_{max} 515, 647, 771, 856, 926, 1073, 1156, 1370, 1482, 1629, 2362, 2838 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (δ , CDCl_3) 7.93 (1H, d, J 7.5 Hz, H-5), 7.90 (1H, dd, J 7.5 and 2.5 Hz, H-6'), 7.75 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz, H-5''), 7.49 (3H, m, H-6, H-2' and H-5'), 7.16 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz, H-4''), 6.77 (1H, s, H-3), 4.09 (6H, s, 2 \times OMe), MS m/z (rel. int.) 325 (M^+ +3, 7.2), 307 (1.8), 292 (100), 264 (3.6), 165 (5.0), 162 (35.5), 160 (16.3), 131 (2.6), 116 (2.1), 90 (1.7).

Antimicrobial activity : The antimicrobial activity was achieved according to the method described in Garg⁸ (1961 and Thornberry⁹).

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